

LOCATION DATA IN ECOLOGICAL RESEARCH

ARTURO H. ARIÑO

UNIVERSITY OF NAVARRA :: AMBIUN :: BEQ :: BIOMA INSTITUTE

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Errebelu, Navarra. © Arturo H. Ariño, 2011

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A.H. ARIÑO, LOCATION DATA IN ECOLOGICAL RESEARCH. MOBILISE, WARSAW 10-II-2020

RONDÔNIA, BRAZIL

MODIS instrument aboard TERRA. Goddard Space Flight Center, NASA.

U.S. Geological Survey

2000 2001 2002 2003 2004 2005 2006 2007 2008 2009 2010 2011 2012

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RONDÔNIA, BRAZIL

Image by Robert Simmon & Reto Stöckli, NASA.

SOME EXAMPLES

Pollination decays in biodiversity hotspots

Jana C. Vamوسي^{1*}, Tiffany M. Knight², Janette A. Steets³, Susan J. Mazer⁴, Martin Burd⁵, and Tia-Ly

¹Department of Biological Sciences, University of Calgary, 2500 University Drive NW, Calgary, AB, Canada T2N 1N6; ²Department of Biology, University of Missouri, Columbia, MO 65211; ³Department of Biological Sciences, University of Pittsburgh, Pittsburgh, PA 15260; ⁴Department of Evolution, and Marine Biology, University of California, Santa Barbara, CA 93106; and ⁵School of Biological Sciences, Monash U 3800, Australia

Edited by May R. Berenbaum, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, Urbana, IL, and approved December 6, 2005 (received October 12, 2005)

As pollinators decline globally, competition for their services is expected to intensify, and this antagonism may be most severe where the number of plant species is the greatest. Using meta-analysis and comparative phylogenetic analyses, we provide a global-scale test of whether reproduction becomes more limited by pollen receipt (pollen limitation) as the number of coexisting plant species increases. As predicted, we find a significant positive relationship between pollen limitation and species richness. In addition, this pattern is particularly strong for species that are obligately outcrossing and for trees relative to herbs or shrubs. We suggest that plants occurring in species-rich communities may be more prone to pollen limitation because of interspecific competition for pollinators. As a consequence, plants in biodiversity hotspots may have a higher risk of extinction and/or experience increased selection pressure to specialize on certain pollinators or diversify into different phenological niches. The combination of higher pollen limitation and habitat destruction represents a dual risk to tropical plant species that has not been previously identified.

extinction | latitudinal gradients | speciation | competition | pollen delivery

Wild plant species in biodiversity hotspots are an important world resource for the products and ecosystem services they provide, including medicine, food, nutrient cycling, and alternative resources for pollinators of domesticated crops (1). Maintaining plant biodiversity in hotspots is a critical challenge for conservation biologists because individual species may have reduced mean fitness in species-rich communities because of increased interspecific competition (2–4). In flowering plants, the presence of coflowering species can reduce pollination success at a local scale because of reduced visitation of generalist pollinators to the focal species, decreased delivery of conspecific pollen, or stigma interference by heterospecific pollen (5–8). However, whether the number of competing species within broad geographic regions influences global patterns in pollination biology has not yet been examined.

Adaptations for effective pollination are widely accepted to have contributed to the tremendous radiation of angiosperms (9, 10). Pollen limitation may decrease as plants evolve traits that reduce reliance on pollinators (e.g., self-compatible breeding systems and vegetative reproduction), attract more specialized pollinators that deliver less heterospecific pollen, or reduce competition for pollinators (e.g., shifts in flowering time) (11). Studies have found that diversity in flowering phenologies and pollinator fauna is indeed higher in species-rich areas (12, 13). If plants in species-rich regions are more often pollen limited than those in species-depauperate areas, they may experience relatively strong natural selection favoring traits that reduce pollen limitation, making current biodiversity hotspots an even more valuable global resource as centers for future adaptation and, potentially, speciation.

We evaluate the potential effect of regional species diversity on the magnitude of pollen limitation by investigating a number of mitigating factors. First, we examine whether the number of observed pollinating taxa affected the relationship between

pollen limitation and species richness whether this relationship varies with dependence on pollinator abundance. We expect that self-incompatible pollinators for pollen transfer than self-compatible ones, therefore, may be more vulnerable to pollen limitation. We also investigate the effect of growth form on pollen limitation, the mean distance between plants in regions may exceed the mean interplant distance for most pollinator species (15), whereas shrubs, interplant spacing may still be within pollinator foraging distances.

A strong positive relationship between species richness and pollen limitation may identify a plant species' neighbors and intensity of selection on many attributes of plant-animal relationships such as flowering phenology, breeding systems, and dispersal patterns in pollination success are important but species richness is undoubtedly a factor that make it difficult to identify increased pollen limitation. First, it is that confer higher magnitudes of pollen limitation in species-rich regions (e.g., species experience greater pollen limitation in species-rich areas). Second, sister taxa in species-rich regions (e.g., species) bias the apparent relationship between regional species richness. Although such as presence in forested or open habitats, phenotypic in the conventional sense more similar in these traits, and sister taxa as an independent data point in cross-species analyses is a form of conservatism that reduce these sources of bias (12), we perform phylogenetic analyses between sister taxa that differ in outbreeding and regional species richness.

Results

Our data set was comprised of pollen limitation data from 60°N to 40°S in latitude (Fig. 1) distributed among all major angiosperm clades. The relatively low number of pollen limitation data conducted in areas of either very low species richness (DZ 1) or very high species richness (DZ 10), we find a strong positive relationship between species richness and the magnitude of pollen limitation (Fig. 1). This global-scale pattern is consistent with the idea that competition among coflowering

Conflict of interest statement: No conflicts declared. This paper was submitted directly (Track II) to the PNAS journal. *To whom correspondence should be addressed. E-mail: jvamوسي@ucalgary.ca. © 2006 by The National Academy of Sciences of the USA.

NITROGEN FERTILIZATION

ARIÑO, A.H., GIMENO, B.S., PÉREZ DE ZABALZA, A., IBÁÑEZ, R., EDERRA, A., AND SANTAMARÍA, J.M. Influence of nitrogen deposition on plant biodiversity at Natura 2000 sites in Spain. En: Hicks W.K., Whitfield C.P., Bealey W.J., Sutton M.A. (Eds.), *Nitrogen and Natura 2000: Science and practice in determining environmental impacts. COST729, ESF. ISBN 978-91-86125-23-3. Págs. 140-146*

Nitrophilic plants increased over the XXth century in Spain associated to critical loads of atmospheric reactive nitrogen. Discovered through georeferenced GBIF historical data.

Nitrophilic plant index derived from GBIF

The value of georeferenced collection records predicting patterns of mosquito species richness and endemism in the Neotropics

DESMOND H. FOLEY¹, ANNA L. WEITZMAN², SCOTT MICHAEL E. FARAN³, LEOPOLDO M. RUEDA¹ and RICHARD WILKERSON¹ ¹Division of Entomology, Walter Reed Army Institute of Research, Silver Spring, MD, U.S.A., ²National Museum of Natural History, Smithsonian Institution, Washington DC, U.S.A., ³Department of Tropical Medicine, Walter Reed Army Medical Center, Honolulu, Hawaii, U.S.A.

Abstract. 1. Determining large-scale distribution patterns of mosquitoes requires knowledge of global mosquito biogeography and information on mosquito inventory needs are greatest.

2. Over 43 000 georeferenced records are presented of mosquitoes from collections undertaken between 1899 and 1999 in 42 countries throughout the Neotropics. Of 492 species in the database, 100 were recorded from one location, and *Anopheles albimanus* Wiedemann was the most common species.

3. A linear log–log species–area relationship was found for the Neotropics and country area. Chile had the lowest relative density of species per area, followed by Panama and French Guiana.

4. The potential distribution of species was predicted using the Environmental Niche Modelling (ENM) approach. *Anopheles* species had the largest potential distribution, whereas species of *Deinocerites* and *Wyeomyia* had the smallest.

5. Species richness was estimated for 1° grids and by summing species from ENM. These methods both showed areas of high species richness in French Guiana, Panama, Trinidad-Tobago, and Colombia. Potential hotspots were identified in Panama, French Guiana, Colombia, Belize, and Venezuela.

6. Argentina, The Bahamas, Bermuda, Bolivia, Cuba, and other countries in the database compared with known species richness data. Analysis of species accumulation curves suggested paucity of data points, which may affect estimates of species richness.

7. The data set is a first step towards the development of georeferenced mosquito collection records.

Key words. BIOCLIM, biogeography, collections, databases, Neotropics, species–area relationship, species endemism, species richness.

Introduction

With the advent of powerful tools enabling the use of museum specimen data for addressing questions in global biogeography, climate change, vector control, and conservation, there is an

Correspondence: Desmond H. Foley, Smithsonian Institution MSC MRC534, 4210 Silver Hill Road, Suitland MD 20746, U.S.A. E-mail: foleydes@si.edu

increasing need for continental-scale insect specimen data (Turner *et al.* 2004). Although, continental scale data exist for butterflies (e.g. Soberon *et al.*, 2004), they lag far behind plants and vertebrates in the amount of data.

For mosquitoes, georeferenced collections databases of large geographic scale exist but are usually not digitised or comprise unpublished survey and museum collection records. The paucity

indicated a high species richness); and infrastructure bias (e.g. over-sampling near roads and towns). An additional source of bias is reporting bias (i.e. not reporting unsuccessful attempts to collect mosquitoes). Sampling bias will favour certain spe-

cies, so the database should be viewed as a record of species presence rather than absence.

It was beyond the scope of this study to evaluate the ecological realism of distribution models. Estimates of species ranges

Fig. 6. Observed species richness for 1-degree grids calculated in DIVA-GIS from 1853 locations.

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Journal compilation © 2007 The Royal Entomological Society, *Ecological Entomology*, 33, 12–23

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Journal compilation © 2007 The Royal Entomological Society

SHIFTS FROM CLIMATE CHANGE

ENMs for species of edaphic Collembola responding to subtle climate variations in nature reserves, from field samplings georeferenced at metric resolution and modelled on BIOCLIM at sub-km resolution

Baquero E., Ariño A.H., Jordana R. BioECNA Final Report. 2015

Photos: E. Baquero

Movement ecology of migration in turkey vultures

J. T. Mandel, K. L. Bildstein, G. Bohrer, and D. W. Winkler
 PNAS December 9, 2008 105 (49) 19102-19107; <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0801789105>
 Edited by Ran Nathan, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Jerusalem, Israel, and accepted August 25, 2008 (received for review February 26, 2008)

Article Figures & SI Info & Metrics

Abstract

We develop individual-based movement ecology models (MEM) to explain (*Cathartes aura*) migration decisions at both hourly and daily scales. Ten migration events were recorded with satellite-reporting GPS sensors and were observed visually, aided by on-the-ground VHF radio-tracking. We used the National Centers for Environmental Prediction North American Regional Reanalysis dataset to obtain values for wind speed, kinetic energy (TKE), and cloud height and used a digital elevation model for terrain ruggedness. A turkey vulture fitted with a heart-rate logger during 12 contiguous days showed only a small increase in mean heart rate as day increased, which suggests that, unlike flapping, soaring flight does not increase metabolic costs. Data from 10 migrations for 724 hourly segments showed that vultures depended heavily upon high levels of atmospheric boundary layer to increase flight distances and maintain both hourly and daily scales. We suggest how the MEM can be extended to other temporal scales of avian migration. Our success in relating model variables to migration indicates the potential of using regional reanalysis data and potentially other regional, higher-resolution, atmospheric models in predicting movement patterns of soaring birds under various scenarios of climate and land use change.

Effective fisheries management instrumental in improving fish stock status

Ray Hilborn^{1,2}, Ricardo Oscar Amoroso³, Christopher M. Anderson³, Julia K. Baum⁴, Trevor A. Branch⁵, Christopher Costello⁶, Carryn L. de Moor⁷, Abdelmalek Faraj⁸, Daniel Hively⁹, Olaf P. Jensen¹⁰, Hiroyuki Kuroki¹¹, Richard Little¹², Pamela Maø¹³, Tim McClanahan¹⁴, Michael C. Melnychuk¹⁵, Cólín Minto¹⁶, Giacomo Chato O'Ana M. Parma¹⁷, Maite Pons¹⁸, Susana Segurado¹⁹, Cody S. Szuwalski²⁰, Jono R. Wilson²¹, and Yimin Ye²²

¹School of Aquatic and Fishery Sciences, University of Washington, Seattle, WA 98195; ²Department of Biology, University of Victoria, Victoria, BC, Canada; ³Bren School of Environmental Science and Management, University of California, Santa Barbara, CA 93117; ⁴Marine Resource Management Group, Department of Mathematics and Applied Mathematics, University of Cape Town, 7701 Rondebosch, South Africa; ⁵Institut de Recerca Halieutica, Casablanca, 20100, Morocco; ⁶Department of Marine and Coastal Sciences, Rutgers University, New Brunswick, NJ 08903; ⁷National Fisheries Research Institute, Japan Fisheries Research and Education Agency, Nagasaki-shi, 851-2213 Nagasaki, Japan; ⁸Marine Resources Program, CSIRO Oceans and Atmosphere, Hobart, TAS 7001, Australia; ⁹Fisheries New Zealand, Ministry for Primary Industries, Wellington, New Zealand; ¹⁰Global Marine Program, Wildlife Conservation Society, Bronx, NY 10460; ¹¹Marine and Freshwater Research Centre, Galway Marine Technology, Galway, H91 1BNW, Ireland; ¹²Unit D.02 Water and Marine Resources, Directorate for D-Sustainable Resources, Joint Research Centre Commission, 21027 Ispra, Italy; ¹³Unit D.1 Fisheries Conservation and Control in Mediterranean and Black Sea, DG Maritime Affairs and Fisheries Commission, JI-99 0246, B-1049 Brussels, Belgium; ¹⁴Centro para el Estudio de Sistemas Marinos, Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas 9120 ACF Puerto Madryn, Chubut, Argentina; ¹⁵Systems Division, Sustainable Fisheries Partnership, Honolulu, HI 96816; ¹⁶California Oceans Program, Conservancy, San Francisco, CA 94110; and ¹⁷Fisheries and Aquaculture Department, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, 00

Edited by Nils Chr. Stenseth, University of Oslo, Oslo, Norway, and approved November 15, 2019 (received for review June 12, 2019)

Marine fish stocks are an important part of the world food system and are particularly important for many of the poorest people of the world. Most existing analyses suggest overfishing is increasing, and there is widespread concern that fish stocks are decreasing throughout most of the world. We assembled trends in abundance and harvest rate of stocks that are scientifically assessed, constituting half of the reported global marine fish catch. For these stocks, on average, abundance is increasing and is at proposed target levels. Compared with regions that are intensively managed, regions with less-developed fisheries management have, on average, 3-fold greater harvest rates and half the abundance as assessed stocks. Available evidence suggests that the regions without assessments of abundance have little fisheries management, and stocks are in poor shape. Increased application of area-appropriate fisheries science recommendations and management tools are still needed for sustaining fisheries in places where they are lacking.

overfishing | harvest impacts | sustainable fisheries

In the mid-1970s, national and international efforts to sustain and rebuild marine fisheries and increase their contribution to global food security led most coastal states to declare 200-nautical mile exclusive economic zones. These moves were further incorporated into the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea, which came into force after 1994. Through the 1970s and 1980s, it became clear that many fisheries were overcapitalized and that fish stocks were depleted to low levels (1). Major declines in a number of fisheries were observed; for example, most of the herring stocks of the northeast Atlantic had declined markedly or collapsed during the late 1960s and early 1970s (2, 3). Moreover, Peruvian anchoveta declined in the 1970s (4), and the Newfoundland cod fishery collapsed (5). These collapses set the stage for both increased concern about the status of fish stocks and a wide variety of actions to reverse the declines, including strengthening the legal basis for addressing overfishing in some countries (6). The intensity and effectiveness of these efforts differs greatly by region, with some countries failing to reduce overfishing and others implementing major regulatory changes.

Declines of fish stocks became the subject of high-profile scientific publications, media coverage, and public interest in the 1990s and 2000s, when the global fisheries crisis perception was established (see, e.g., ref. 7). In response, Worm et al. (8) published a summary of the biomass trends of marine fish stocks from regions in which scientific data were available up to 2005. The compilation showed that while two-thirds of stocks were below

fisheries management biomass targets, most biomass with declines occurring in some regions and increases in others, and that half of the stocks below target exploitation rates that would allow rebuilding to target suggested a potential relationship between fish stock and management actions. Low stock abundance has negative effects: the sustainable yield is lower, so contribute less to food production and the cost of fisheries rises when abundance is low. Low abundance also system services such as food provisioning to other

Significance

This article compiles estimates of the status of fish stocks from all available scientific assessments, comprising half of the world's fish catch, and shows that, on average, abundance is increasing where they are assessed. We provide evidence of the nature and extent of fisheries management and demonstrate that where fisheries are intensively managed the stocks are above target levels or rebuilding, whereas where management is less intense, stock status and trends are poorer. We review evidence on the half of world fisheries that are assessed or intensively managed and suggest that they are much worse than where fisheries are intensively

Author contributions: R.H., R.O.A., C.M.A., J.K.B., T.A.B., C.C., C.L.H.K., L.R.L., P.M., M.C.M., C.M., G.C.O., A.M.P., M.P., S.S., C.S., and D.H. designed research; R.H., R.O.A., C.C., D.H., M.C.M., and C.M. analyzed data; R.H., T.A.B., C.C., C.L.H.K., A.F., D.H., O.P.J., H.K., L.R.L., P.G.C., A.M.P., M.P., S.S., C.S.S., J.R.W., and Y.Y. wrote the paper; C.L.H.K., A.F., D.H., H.K., L.R.L., P.M., M.C.M., C.M., G.C.O., A.M.P., and Y.Y. assembled or provided data.

Competing Interest statement: All authors are involved in fisheries management and provide fisheries advice in ways that can be viewed as competing interests. Some authors are employed by national fisheries agencies or nongovernmental organizations for specific fisheries policies. The academic scientists have received funding from government fisheries agencies, fishing companies, and nongovernmental organizations.

This article is a PNAS Direct Submission.

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Data deposition: Code used for analysis is held in the following GitHub repository: github.com/minto/npnas_efm_pa_per.

¹To whom correspondence may be addressed. Email: hilborn@gmail.com.

This article contains supporting information online at <https://www.pnas.org/lookup/suppl/doi:10.1073/pnas.190926116/-/DCSupplemental>.

First published January 13, 2020.

Pole-to-pole biogeography of surface and deep marine bacterial communities

Jean-François Ghiglione, Pierre E. ...
Elizabeth W. Maas, Kevin Bakker, S...
Patricia L. Yager, and Alison E. Mur...
PNAS October 23, 2012 109 (43) 17633-176...
Edited by David M. Karl, University of Hawai...
14, 2012)

Article

Figures & S...

Abstract

The Antarctic and Arctic regions offer unique insights into the evolution of marine microbial communities because of similar selection pressures. Here, we compared surface and deep diversity between polar oceans, using 16S rDNA sequencing. The small subunit ribosomal (SSU) rDNA sequences of surface and deep communities were included, providing a global perspective. Surface ocean surface communities were more similar to the Southern Ocean and 70% of surface communities were more similar to the Arctic Ocean. Analyses of depths, seasons, and depths of bacterioplankton communities compared Southern and Arctic Ocean communities. In contrast, deep ocean communities were more similar in deep waters and displayed different diversity patterns compared to surface communities. Estimated diversity (Chao1) for surface and deep communities did not correlate with latitude or temperature. Our results suggest differences in environmental conditions at the poles and different selection mechanisms controlling surface and deep ocean community structure and diversity. Surface bacterioplankton may be subjected to more short-term, variable conditions, whereas deep communities appear to be structured by longer water-mass residence time and connectivity through ocean circulation.

3-D GEOREFERENCING

Mismatches between demographic niches and geographic distributions are strong for poorly dispersed and highly persistent species

Jörn Pagel, Martina Treurnicht, William J. Bond, Tineke Kraaij, Henning Nottebrock, AnneLise Schutte-Vlok, Jeanne Tonnabel, Frank M. Schurr

PNAS first published February 6, 2020 <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1908684117>
 Edited by Susan Harrison, University of California, Davis, CA, and approved January 3, 2020 (2019)

Article Figures & SI Info & Metrics

Significance

Forecasts of global change impacts on biodiversity often assume that the geographical distributions of species match their ecological niches. Here, we use an assumption using an extensive dataset of large-scale variation in demographic parameters to quantify demography-based ecological niches of 26 plant species. Contrasting these niches with the species' geographic distributions reveals that distribution mismatches can be large and depend on key life-history traits. Species are absent from suitable sites, and species with high persistence are present in sites that are currently unsuitable for them. Such niche–distribution mismatches should be accounted for to improve forecasts of biodiversity dynamics under environmental change.

ACQUIRING URBAN ENVIRONMENTAL DATA

Very-high resolution geolocated data for portable atmospheric analyzers enable cartographing the fine scale pollution levels in space and time, validating biological indicators

Ariño A.H., Santamaría J.M., et al – LIFE+RESPIRA Final Report. 2018

1 billion reads 1 0 1 2 3 4 km

DOES ECOLOGY REQUIRE LOCATION DATA?

Ecology deals with biodiversity, ecosystems, and processes.

Ecosystems are happenings of biodiversity undergoing processes over time.

Space and time mandate, create, modulate all three.

Knowledge of the What, **Where** and When is bundled in the biodiversity data

Let's mine www for **WWW** . . .

PEERING INTO LITERATURE

*Ariño A.H., 2020.
Working dataset
mobilise/warsaw/geogata.
xlsx. Multiple sources.
Queried Dec. 2019-Feb.
2020. Unpublished results.*

FREQUENCY ANALYSIS

- Exploring **Data Gaps** at the Species Level: Starting with demographic **knowledge**
- Results of IndexMed GRAIL Days 2016: How to use **standards** to build GRAPhs and mine **data** for environmental **research**
- Applying **TDWG Standards** to assess the **Ecosystem** Value of UNESCO Man and Biosphere **Reserves** in **Africa**.
- **Citizen science** and expert **community** interactions using Wikwio, a weed **knowledge** portal, focused on southern **Africa**
- Mamut: An online web editor to manage **biological information** of **taxa** based on the Plinian Core
- **Data** Quality Workflows using Akka
- **Potential** of mobile search logs in **citizen science** context for biodiversity monitoring

Normalized term

3	data
2	standard
2	knowledge
2	africa
2	citizen
2	science
1	information
1	research
1	ecosystem
1	taxa
1	tdwg
1	gap
1	potential
1	reserve
1	community
1	Biology
2	...

0.0% 0.5% 1.0% 1.5% 2.0% 2.5% 3.0% 3.5% 4.0%

Relative frequency of normalized terms extracted from the titles of papers published since 1900 on PNAS about Ecology (yellow) and Ecology requiring or dealing with georeferencing (red)

Ariño A.H., 2020. Working dataset mobilise/warsaw/geogata.xlsx. PNAS subset of 1500 papers downloaded Feb. 2020. Unpublished results.

■ Used geodata
■ Ecology papers

SWEEPING THE STAKES

*Ariño A.H., 2020.
Working dataset
mobilise/warsaw/geogata.
xlsx. PNAS subset of 1500
papers downloaded Feb.
2020. Unpublished results.*

Growth in papers on subjects over time (relative to each subject). 5-year periods after 2005, 15-year periods before. Georeferenced papers came later into the game but are now stronger.

SOURCES: NHC, PRIMARY BIODIVERSITY DATA

David Galicia, © Universidad de Navarra

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mobilise

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Research applications of primary biodiversity databases in the digital age

Joan E. Ball-Damerow^{1*}, Laura Brenskelle², Narayani Barve², Pamela S. Soltis², Petra Sierwald¹, Rüdiger Bieler¹, Raphael LaFrance², Arturo H. Ariño³, Robert P. Guralnick²

OPEN ACCESS

Citation: Ball-Damerow JE, Brenskelle Soltis PS, Sierwald P, Bieler R, et al. (2019) Research applications of primary biodiversity databases in the digital age. PLoS ONE 14(9): e0215794. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0215794>

Editor: Daniel de Paiva Silva, Instituto Educacao Ciencia e Tecnologia Golang Urutal, BRAZIL

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Data Availability Statement: The data underlying this article are published in open access article and can be found at: <https://zenodo.org/record/2598439#XXKXWUuKJBI> (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2598439).

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Data Type	Species Distribution	Diversity/ Population	Data Paper	Taxonomy	Conservation	Data Quality
Climate	58	37	7	2	32	26
Literature	41	40	29	52	40	26
Geographic	37	31	11	2	34	21
Surveys	36	36	29	32	32	13
Habitat	30	34	18	11	43	21
Collection	28	23	44	53	18	22
Traits	25	25	15	26	25	13
Conservation	20	29	9	15	75	15
Expert	15	7	9	3	22	7
Private	15	13	8	5	10	7
Range	14	12	6	5	22	13
Catalogues	11	18	20	25	19	22
Hydrography	11	12	3	2	16	1
Soil	11	11	2	0	10	3
Ecoregion	10	24	8	6	19	7
Genetic	10	13	24	26	6	6
Social	10	7	4	1	13	7
Interaction	9	5	4	8	6	0
Paleo Climate	7	5	1	0	1	0
Image	5	4	21	23	1	7
Phylogenetic	5	11	12	16	1	4

<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0215794.t005>

GBIF INDEX

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GBIF | Global Biodiversity Information Facility

Acceso libre y gratuito a los datos de biodiversidad

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WHAT IS GBIF? ABOUT GBIF POLAND

Golden leatherfern (*Acrostichum aureum*) collected near Hinda, Republic of the Congo by E. Bidault. Photo via The Missouri Botanical Garden's Herbarium (CC BY-NC-ND 3.0)

Occurrence records
1.389.795.585

Datasets
50.446

Publishing institutions
1567

Peer-reviewed papers using data
4217

Virtual workshop planned on "Advancing the Catalogue of the World's Natural History Collections"

Call for nominations to the 2020 GBIF Young Researchers Award

Global analysis of potential marginal land resources of cassava

The Equator Principles encourage open access to environmental impact data through the GBIF network

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GBIF RECORDS IN LITERATURE

Sources

The articles are retrieved using alerts and XML-based feeds from the following sources:

Source	Medium
Google Scholar	e-mail
Scopus	e-mail
Wiley Online Library	e-mail
SpringerLink	RSS feed
NCBI Pubmed	e-mail
Crossref Event Data	API

SPECIES
 MODELING
 DISTRIBUTION
 CLIMATE
 BIODIVERSITY

Ariño A.H., Noesgaard D., Hjarding A., Schigel D., 2018. Biodiversity Information Services: A (not-so-) little knowledge that acts. Biodiversity Information Science and Standards 2: e25378.

Ranks by frequency of author keywords in papers using GBIF-facilitated data over time. Stable themes: core usage of primary biodiversity data records (PBR).

Ranks by frequency usage of author keywords in papers using GBIF-facilitated data over time. Themes emerging at the wake of generalized georeferencing.

Ariño A.H., Noesgaard D., Hjarding A., Schigel D., 2018. Biodiversity Information Services: A (not-so-) little knowledge that acts. Biodiversity Information Science and Standards 2: e25378.

INVASIONS
 SDM
 BIOGEOGRAPHY
 ENM
 MAXENT

Ranks by frequency
 usage of author
 keywords in papers
 using GBIF-facilitated
 data over time.
 Emergent themes
 strongly dependent on
 availability of quality
 georeferenced data.

*Ariño A.H., Noesgaard D.,
 Hjarding A., Schigel D.,
 2018. Biodiversity
 Information Services: A
 (not-so-) little knowledge
 that acts. Biodiversity
 Information Science and
 Standards 2: e25378.*

DATA AVAILABLE THROUGH GBIF

▼
< 1800 . 1820 . 1840 . 1860 . 1900 . 1920 . 1940 . 1960 . 1980 . 2000 . 2020 >

GEOREFERENCING THE BACKLOG

Fraction of records in the GBIF index that are georeferenced by time epochs (note decreasing widths) for the whole index and the Museum collections

Ariño A.H., 2020. Filters on the main GBIF index applied Feb. 2020. Unpublished results.

GEOQUALITY, ANYONE?

SWEET [FAMILIAR] HOME

Ariño A.H., Robles E., 2007. Patterns in biodiversity records digitised from literature. *Proceedings of TDWG*, 2007, 82-83.

Classes: binary logs of distance recorded event – digitizing laboratory and of implicit precision. Size: number of records in dataset. From the Zootron 4 database.

A CONVENIENT TRUTH . . .

Publisher: Norwegian

Publisher: Swedish

Publisher: German

Publisher: British

Publisher: Parisien

Publisher: French

Publisher: Spanish

Data records added by specific data providers according to nationality or region, color-coded. Preference for staying within borders. May induce unevenness.

Otegui J., Robles E., Ariño A.H., 2009. Noise in Biodiversity Data. International Conference on Biodiversity Informatics (e-biosphere), London.

RETRO PRECISION

Declared vs implicit precision in GBIF records. Left: potentially accurate records; right: uncertainty possibly derived from implicit precision

Ariño A.H., 2020.
Working dataset
mobilise/warsaw/0008129
-200127171203522.xlsx.
GBIF. Queried Feb., 2020.
Unpublished results.

Implicit precision in latitude vs longitude for GBIF records.
 Diagonal: Consistent.
 H0 (2-dimensional lognormal curves) might be warranted.

Ariño A.H., 2020.
 Working dataset
 mobilise/warsaw/0008129
 -200127171203522.xlsx.
 GBIF. Queried Feb., 2020.
 Unpublished results.

WINDING DOWN – OR UP?

Ariño A.H., 2020.
Working dataset
mobilise/warsaw/0008129
-200127171203522.xlsx.
GBIF. Queried Feb., 2020.
Unpublished results.

Fraction of georeferenced (=with coordinates) records in the GBIF index that include uncertainty (e.g. point-radius) by date of event (=collection date)

BETTER GEOREFERENCING STANDARDS

Fraction of georeferenced (=with coordinates) records in the GBIF index that include uncertainty (e.g. point-radius) by date of upload to the index

*Ariño A.H., 2020.
Working dataset
mobilise/warsaw/0008129
-200127171203522.xlsx.
GBIF. Queried Feb., 2020.
Unpublished results.*

1790

Airilño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1800

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1810

Airilño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1820

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

Airilño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

1830

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1840

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

Airilño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15

1850

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1860

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1870

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1880

Airilño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

1890

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

Airilño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15

1900

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

Airilño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3

1910

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15

1920

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1930

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1940

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1950

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3

- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1960

- 0
- 1
- 2
- 3

- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1970

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1980

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

1990

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

2000

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

2010

All georeferenced data at 1/100 degree – Occurrences

Ariño A.H., Otegui J, Villarroya A., Pérez de Zabalza A.I., 2012. Primary biodiversity data records in the Pyrenees. Environmental Engineering and Management Journal, 11(6): 1059-1075

Georeferencing into or from tile- or gridded-type distribution data in GBIF records from the Pyrenean range. Distinctive regular pattern. Fit for some uses.

- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15

+

30.37,	-87.1765
48.5584,	-123.463
42.3487,	-123.78
41.7866,	-100.061
-73.9071,	42.7028
38.8749,	-104.88
44.3964,	-75.6668
42.1927,	-89.106
32.693,	-79.9606
44.2124,	-88.42
41.6637,	-
39.6992,	-
46.13,	-72
38.7231,	-
27.7349,	-
36.0852,	-121.616
39.0901,	-77.5203
-83.1662,	43.0622
41.2956,	-74.5956
45.5146,	-73.8131
42.0755,	-122.759
41.1047,	-81.4944
42.4792,	-89.0333
40.6956,	-74.8913
...	

Otegui J., Ariño A.H., 2009. Have Standards Enhanced Biodiversity Data? Correction and acquisition patterns in GBIF Proceedings of TDWG, 2009.

Routine detection and correction of georeferencing errors. Swapped coordinates in a data provided.

Latitude ↔ Longitude

OMNIPRESENT GAPS

Otegui J., Ariño A.H., Encinas M.A., Panfido F. 2013 Assessing the Primary Data Hosted by the Spanish Node of the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). *PLoS One*, 8 (1), e55144. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0055144>

(Mis)DIRECTED EFFORTS

Differences between number of species based on existing data and expected number of species based on expert judgement

Meyer, Kreft, Guralnick, Jetz: Global priorities for an effective information basis of biodiversity distributions. *Nature Communications* 6:822. DOI: 10.1038/ncomms9221

BUT - WARNING . . .

Universidad
de Navarra

mobilise

DATA NOISE: RISKS

- Inference coming from **vast** amounts of data
- Some data may be **inaccurate**: Incorrect conclusions, inability to draw theories

Anoplogaster cornuta

Search occurrences

Use the filters to customize search results

383

Occurrences

[Download](#)

383 results

[\[View results as map\]](#)

[Configure](#) [Add a filter](#)

BASIS OF RECORD

COUNTRY

SCIENTIFIC NAME

Refine your search

[reset](#)

BASIS OF RECORD

Specimen (383)

TYPE STATUS

Holotype (1)

DATASET

- Estacion Biologica Donan... (205)
- Natural History Museum (... (104)
- Museo Nacional de Ciencia... (45)
- Museo Nacional de Ciencia... (10)
- AMNH Bird Collection (9)
- Naturalis Biodiversity Cen... (5)
- Field Museum of Natural Hi... (2)
- Museum of Comparative Zool... (1)
- Museu de Ciències Naturals... (1)
- ORN (1)

[1](#) [>](#)

COUNTRY

Spain (383)

	LOCATION	BASIS OF RECORD	DATE
127220026 · Cat. 11784A Aquila adalberti C. L. Brehm, 1861 Published in Estacion Biologica Donana - CSIC, Aves	Spain N/A	Specimen	6 / 2007
127220532 · Cat. 24465A Aquila adalberti C. L. Brehm, 1861 Published in Estacion Biologica Donana - CSIC, Aves	Spain N/A	Specimen	- / 2004
127220526 · Cat. 24281A Aquila adalberti C. L. Brehm, 1861 Published in Estacion Biologica Donana - CSIC, Aves	Spain N/A	Specimen	2 / 2003
127220520 · Cat. 24274A			

ber 2016

GEOREFERENCING TRADE-OFFS

OWNERS

Ariño A.H., 2017. The case of sensitive georeferenced data in Biodiversity. EUDAT workshop on sensitive data, Helsinki, 2917. Unpublished results.

Factor affecting decisions on release and processing of georeferenced sensitive data

Release

Hold

PUBLIC

GUIDE TO BEST PRACTICES FOR GENERALISING

SENSITIVE SPECIES OCCURENCE DATA

Arthur D. Chapman and
Oliver Grafton

Chapman AD & Grafton O (2008) Guide to Best Practices for Generalising Primary Species-Occurrence Data, version 1.0. Copenhagen: Global Biodiversity Information Facility, 27 pp. ISBN: 87-92020-06-2. Available online at <http://www.gbif.org/resource/80512>.

*“Biodiversity information should be made freely available to be shared globally to enable their use for not-for-profit decision-making, education, research and other public benefit purposes. Making the full detail of biodiversity information available should reduce the risk of damage to the environment and help safeguard a sustainable future. **Where release will have the opposite effect, access to the full detail may need to be controlled.**”*

This work is a contribution of the Biodiversity Data Analytics and Environmental Quality Group (BEQ)
Department of Environmental Biology (AMBIUN), University of Navarra, Pamplona, Spain
within the Biodiversity and Environment Institute (BIOMA)

All images, plots and analyses by the authors except where otherwise noted

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www.ambiun.es

www.unav.edu

No bytes were seriously harmed while preparing this PPTX.
(And copies exist of those who actullay were, anyway).
This file used 328 watt-hours, offset by riding a bike for many years.

